

РАЗДЕЛ. ТЕХНИЧЕСКИЕ НАУКИ

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**NEURAL NETWORKS AS A SURROGATE MODELING METHOD
TO ASSESS THE DYNAMICS OF ACUTE RESPIRATORY
INFECTION PROPAGATION**

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Annotation: Acute respiratory diseases and their associated epidemics impose a significant burden on individuals and societies. Health organizations are interested in determining the dynamics of the spread to determine the timing and form of intervention to reduce the disease burden. Agent-based models ABMs are a promising and effective method for simulating the spread of disease within populations. However, these models suffer from the problem of high computational cost in case of large populations and computation for large parameter space. This article discusses the possibility of using surrogate neural network-based models as an approximation to the ABM so that we can obtain acceptable results in less time.

Keywords: epidemiology, Acute respiratory diseases, Agent-based models, surrogate modeling, data-fit methods, neural network

**НЕЙРОННЫЕ СЕТИ КАК МЕТОД СУРРОГАТНОГО
МОДЕЛИРОВАНИЯ ДЛЯ ОЦЕНКИ ДИНАМИКИ
РАСПРОСТРАНЕНИЯ ОСТРЫХ
РЕСПИРАТОРНЫХ ИНФЕКЦИЙ**

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Аннотация: Острые респираторные заболевания и связанные с ними эпидемии накладывают значительное бремя на отдельных лиц и общество. Организации здравоохранения заинтересованы в определении динамики распространения для определения сроков и формы вмешательства для снижения бремени болезней. Агентные модели АБМ являются перспективным и эффективным методом моделирования распространения заболеваний в популяциях. Однако эти модели страдают от проблемы высоких вычислительных затрат в случае больших популяций и вычислений для большого пространства параметров. В этой статье обсуждается возможность использования суррогатных моделей на основе нейронных сетей в качестве приближения к АБМ, чтобы мы могли получать приемлемые результаты за меньшее время.

Ключевые слова: эпидемиология, острые респираторные заболевания, агентные модели, суррогатное моделирование, методы подгонки данных, нейронная сеть

Introduction:

The spread of respiratory infections is a critical aspect of epidemiological research worldwide and in Russia in particular, where the geographic and demographic diversity is enormous. The Russian surveillance system routinely collects acute respiratory infection data as part of its surveillance activities [1] with the aim of determining the spread dynamics and developing intervention strategies.

ABMs have become a powerful tool in epidemiological modeling due to their ability to simulate interactions between individuals and track the spread of infectious diseases in heterogeneous populations. By simulating each individual's behavior and their contacts, ABMs can model complex processes such as social mixing, disease transmission, and the effects of various interventions [2, 3]. However, the computational expense of ABMs scales with population size and the complexity of interactions, making them impractical for real-time or large-scale applications [4].

Surrogate models aim to approximate the outputs of complex models like ABMs while reducing the computational cost. These models are constructed by training machine learning algorithms on a limited number of simulations from the original ABM, allowing them to predict

model outcomes with much lower computational cost. Techniques such as Gaussian Process Regression are well-suited to surrogate modeling as they provide uncertainty quantification along with predictions [5, 6]. Recently, Neural Networks have also been employed to create surrogate models capable of handling high-dimensional inputs and outputs [7]. In Russia, computationally efficient disease models are critical for managing regional outbreaks, where rapid decision-making is required to allocate resources and implement interventions effectively. In recent years, research in Russia has begun on leveraging advanced modeling techniques, including surrogate modeling, to improve public health outcomes [3, 6].

In our experiment, we discussed the neural networks as a surrogate modeling for ABM that simulate acute respiratory infection propagation in Saint Petersburg.

Experiment:

Data were collected by repeatedly running the agent-based model [8] with different input values: infected = 10 initial number of infected individuals, $\alpha=[0.1,0.99]$ Fraction of non-immune individuals in general population, $\lambda=[0.1,0.99]$ Infection transmission coefficient and Population=[5000,500000] size of the population and the results will be number of infected individuals for days = range(1, 81). as a result the data set contain 1944 rows. each row contains the values α , λ , population and 80 column represent newly infected from day 1 to day 80. The data set was divided into a 80% training set and a 20% test set.

The target data contains a lot of zeros, so we worked on classify the target for zeros and non zeros values and then make regression for non zeros values. for classify the days with zeros and non zeros values, a neural network model was trained (3 layers, 2 BatchNorm1d between them, dropout before the output layer, relu activation function for first two layers and sigmoid for the output) and for regression the values of non zeros days another neural network model was trained (3 layers, relu activation function for first two layers and linear for the output). The models trained for 1000 epoch with use of binary cross entropy, mean square error as loss function and learning rate equal to 0.001.

Results:

The results show that the test accuracy for the classifier is 0.87 and the mean absolute error (MAE) for regression is 59.39. The classification accuracy is considered good but we can not consider the MAE for

regression to be good. We notice from the (fig. 1) the under fitting in regression model.

The positive result of this experiment is that the problem of many zeros in the output sequence can be solved by applying classification. The learning curve for classification in the (fig. 1) shows that accuracy could be improved by tuning model parameters or we can try some advanced network like convolutional neural network for improving accuracy.

Figure 1 – The learning curves for classification and regression

Mapping between some values as input and sequences of multiples values as output is uncommon in machine learning problem. The results confirm the poor performance of the neural network model in solving the problem. We believe that adding a small part of the output chain to the model input and using a LSTM with attention mechanism can give good results in this problem and this is what we are working on.

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